

Wavefunction Squared as Spatial Probability Density

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In a previous note it was argued that $\ln(W(x))$ where $W(x)$ is the wavefunction acted as a kind of partition function which reproduced the classical conservation of energy ($KE + PE = E$) although for average values. In this note, we wish to show how these ideas lead to $W(x)^2$ representing the spatial probability density (for a bound state) using conditional probabilities. We are not aware of this approach having already been presented in the literature.

In [2], it was noted that the average kinetic energy in a quantum bound system could be written as:

$$\sum_p \frac{p^2}{2m} \sin(px) f(p) / \left\{ \sum_p \sin(px) f(p) \right\} \quad (1)$$

One is making use of a Fourier transform here with $f(p)$ the Fourier transform of $W(x)$ the wavefunction. (We use $\sin(px)$ in the Fourier transform as an example of a system with a certain symmetry. The arguments would also hold for $\cos(px)$ instead.

$W(x)$ is the denominator of (1). (1) is consistent with the time independent Schrodinger equation, but as argued in [2] $\sin(px)$ is composed of $\exp(ipx)$ and $\exp(-ipx)$ which are believed to be physical and map to the zitterbewegung motion of a particle. (See a description of the 2x2 matrix model [4].)

Thus:

$\sin(px) f(p) / \left\{ \sum_p \sin(px) f(p) \right\}$ acts as the probability to have a value of momentum p at position x i.e. a conditional probability. The denominator is $W(x)$ the wavefunction and $f(p)$ is the Fourier transform of $W(x)$

It can be seen that this probability can even be negative.

The probability can be expressed as $P(p \text{ given } x)$ which is equivalent to $P(p \text{ intersection } x) / P(x)$ from probability theory. Thus, momentum and position cannot be completely independent as argued in [3].

Similarly, one can write $P(x \text{ given } p)$ which should be $P(p \text{ intersection } x) / P(p)$ and should be equivalent to:

$\sin(px) W(x) / \left\{ \sum_x \sin(px) W(x) \right\}$ Here the denominator is $f(p)$, the Fourier transform of the wavefunction.

If one divides the two, one obtains:

$$P(p)/P(x) = f(p)^2 / W(x)^2$$

where $W(x)$ is the wavefunction and $f(p)$ its Fourier transform. Thus, up to a constant factor $P(p) = f(p)^2$ and $P(x) = W(x)^2$ which is the well known result of quantum mechanics, the latter describing spatial probability density. This appears to follow from conditional probabilities.

Aside Related to Time Resonance

Although this note and [2] deal with probabilities, it seems that one must keep in mind that there is a type of resonance occurring in quantum mechanical systems as there is a factor $\exp(iEt)$ from the time dependent Schrodinger equation. In [1], it was argued that this represented a kind of overall zitterbewegung in the quantum system related to the shift from one plane wave (in the Fourier decomposition) to another. It should be noted, however, that there may be different mechanical resonance existing among average values in the system at the same time. For example, it was noted that on average a quantum mechanical system, even in its ground state, preserves the result:

$$\text{Kinetic energy} + \text{Potential energy} = E$$

Here kinetic energy is $\frac{1}{2}mv(x)^2$ and potential energy $V(r)$. Now average kinetic energy can be written as: $\frac{m}{2}v(x)^2$ where $v(x)$ is the rms average velocity at point x . For a harmonic oscillator, however, there is a mechanical resonance for such an equation as is known from classical physics. It has a frequency of $\sqrt{k/m}$. Thus, in the quantum mechanical harmonic oscillator there seem to be two types of periodic motion occurring, one with angular frequency $6.28\sqrt{k/m}$, the mechanical one, and one with $E = 6.28\sqrt{k/m}(n+.5)$. We suggest that it might not be an accident that E contains the mechanical angular frequency with integer or half integer terms. One may argue that the angular frequency appears in E as a phonon could be a driving force acting on the mechanical resonance in the system. This argument might hold for $n \geq 1$. We argue, however, that it might be possible to say that the two angular frequencies should not disrupt each other when the system is in "quantum equilibrium". This appears to hold even in the ground state where not phonon has been added and the "zero point energy" has a frequency which would not "disrupt" the mechanical one.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we have attempted to show that $W(x)W(x)$ is the probability spatial density in a quantum system, where $W(x)$ is the wavefunction. We also point out that even though statistical arguments are being presented for the quantum mechanical system, it still appears that it is a resonance system with $\exp(iEt)$ representing a kind of zitterbewegung motion related to the shifting from one plane wave to another in the Fourier decomposition of $W(x)$ the wavefunction.

[1] Francesco R. Ruggeri 2x2 Matrix Model and the Schrodinger Equation. Zenodo 2018.

[2] Francesco R. Ruggeri InW As a Partition Function. Zenodo Sept. 2018;

[3] U. Klein. The Statistical Origins of Quantum Mechanics. Physics Research International

Volume 2010, Article ID 808424, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1155/2010/808424>

[4] Francesco R. Ruggeri Is Quantum Mechanics Contained in Special Relativity? Zenodo 2018.